

Guardian: Role-Gated MPC Wallets for AI Agents

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Abstract—AI agents on blockchains need wallets that work without human intervention—yet no single component should be trusted with the full private key. Existing approaches force a choice: hot wallets grant autonomy but no constraints; smart accounts enforce on-chain policies but with gas overhead and scoped session keys; and multi-party computation (MPC) wallets—which split a private key into shares so that multiple parties must cooperate to sign, without ever reconstructing the key—treat all co-signers as interchangeable.

We present Guardian Wallet, a role-gated MPC wallet where the private key is split into three shares, each bound to a distinct operational role: the agent (autonomous execution), the governor (policy enforcement), and the sovereign (human oversight). Any two of the three shares can co-sign a transaction—a configuration known as a 2-of-3 threshold—but each pair carries different authority: normal operation, manual override, or emergency bypass. The governor only releases its share after policy checks pass, making the wallet *role-gated*: which pair co-signs determines what is allowed.

We validate this design on Ethereum using the CGGMP threshold ECDSA protocol [1], a cryptographic scheme that produces standard digital signatures through interactive computation between share holders. Key generation completes in 1s with pre-computed auxiliary data, signing takes 1.1s median on localhost, and policy evaluation adds under 2ms. We compare against smart accounts, hosted MPC wallets, and decentralised MPC using verified production deployments.

Index Terms—AI agents, MPC wallets, role-gated signing, policy-gated shares

I. INTRODUCTION

AI agents increasingly operate on public blockchains—trading, managing liquidity, and executing governance votes autonomously [2]–[4]. Each agent needs a private key, but an agent’s key management needs differ from a human’s: it must sign programmatically, around the clock, without human intervention. Yet it is not fully trusted—it may be compromised, misconfigured, or manipulated. *The entity that needs the key most is the one least trusted to hold it alone.*

MPC wallet protocols [1], [5]–[7] split a private key into multiple shares so that a minimum number of them—the threshold—can jointly produce a valid signature, without ever reconstructing the full key. But all existing protocols treat every valid group of co-signers as equivalent. In practice, systems already assign roles informally: Fireblocks [8] labels its three MPC parties “customer, co-signer, recovery”; BitGo [9] distributes keys across “user, BitGo, backup.” This role assignment is universal but informal—it exists in documentation, not in the access-control layer.

This paper focuses on four requirements specific to agent wallets:

1) **Autonomy.** The agent signs without human intervention.

- 2) **Constraints.** Policies limit what the agent can sign.
- 3) **Human override.** The owner can intervene directly.
- 4) **Resilience.** No single failure locks funds permanently.

There are two obvious solutions, and both fall short. The first: the human keeps the key and approves every transaction. This satisfies constraints and override, but the agent is no longer autonomous—it cannot act while the human is asleep, offline, or slow to respond. The second: the human gives the agent a session key—a temporary signing key with limited permissions. The agent is now autonomous, but the session key is a real key. If the agent is compromised, the attacker can sign freely within those permissions, with no further checks at signing time.

The challenge is not choosing between autonomy and constraints, but achieving both simultaneously. Table I shows that existing approaches each satisfy a different subset; none addresses all four.

TABLE I
EXISTING APPROACHES VS. AGENT WALLET REQUIREMENTS.

	<i>Autonomy</i>	<i>Constraints</i>	<i>Override</i>	<i>Resilience</i>
Hot wallet	✓	×	×	×
Smart account (session keys)	✓	✓	✓	×
Hosted MPC / TEE	✓	partial	✓	×
On-chain multisig	partial	partial	✓	✓
Standard MPC (e.g. 2-of-3)	✓	×	partial	✓

Contributions. The individual ideas—threshold signatures, policy enforcement, role-based access—are well established. Our contribution is systematising their combination into a concrete wallet architecture for autonomous agents, and validating it with an open-source implementation:

- 1) **Signing roles.** A construction where each MPC share has a distinct role and the co-signing pair determines what is allowed (Section III). Gating one share on policy ensures most pairs enforce constraints while leaving exactly one bypass path.
- 2) **Validation.** We implement the (2, 3) case as Guardian Wallet and report signing latency, policy overhead, and security properties (Sections IV–VI).
- 3) **Comparison.** We compare against smart accounts, hosted MPC/TEE wallets, and decentralised MPC, grounded in verified production deployments (Section VII).

II. RELATED WORK

MPC signing protocols. Modern protocols for MPC-based ECDSA [1], [6], [10], [11] and Schnorr (FROST [7]) produce signatures through multi-round interaction without reconstructing the key. Generalised access structures [12]–[14] extend *who* can sign but do not map subsets to operational meaning.

Agent wallets. Smart accounts [15], [16] provide on-chain policy enforcement via session keys and guard modules. Hosted MPC/TEE wallets [8], [17] run keys inside hardware enclaves. Lit Protocol [18], [19] distributes signing across equivalent nodes with JavaScript-based policy checks. Alqithami [2] and Shen et al. [4] survey agent-blockchain integration. The MIT Media Lab [20] addresses delegation, and Acharya [21] addresses payment authenticity. The Ethereum community identifies agent key management as an open problem [3].

All deployed MPC and multisig systems we surveyed—Fireblocks, BitGo, Casa, Safe, Lit Protocol, and Shamir backup services—assign roles to shares informally at best. None formalises the connection between which parties co-sign and what is authorised, or couples policy evaluation to share access.

Practitioners already deploy threshold shares to different parties with informal role expectations (e.g., Fireblocks assigns shares to “user, server, recovery”). However, we are not aware of prior work that explicitly formalises the mapping between co-signing pairs and authorisation contexts, or that couples policy evaluation to share access at the application layer. Our contribution is systematising this pattern and evaluating it in the context of autonomous agents.

III. SIGNING ROLES

The gap identified above—role assignment is universal but informal—motivates a construction we call *signing roles*. The idea: in an MPC wallet, each share is assigned a distinct role, and the choice of which shares co-sign determines what kind of operation is authorised. For example, one share might belong to the agent, another to a policy-enforcing server, and a third to the human owner. Different pairs of co-signers then represent different levels of authority—autonomous operation, human override, or emergency bypass.

To make this work, we need a mechanism that connects roles to policy enforcement. We introduce *policy-gated shares*.

A. Policy-Gated Shares

Some shares are *policy-gated*: the system loads them into memory only after all policy checks pass. The remaining shares are *always available*. Any group that includes at least one gated share is constrained; a group with no gated shares bypasses all policies—an emergency path.

The design question: how many shares to gate? Gate too few and multiple co-signing pairs bypass policies entirely. Gate too many and there is no bypass at all—a policy engine crash locks funds permanently.

The rule: gate exactly one share fewer than the threshold. This ensures that almost every co-signing pair includes a gated share (and therefore enforces policies), while leaving exactly one pair that can sign without any infrastructure. In the (2, 3) case: one gated share, two ungated, three possible pairs—two go through policies, one bypasses them.

B. Properties

Liveness. At least one co-signing pair requires no gated infrastructure. No policy failure, server crash, or network outage permanently locks funds—provided the ungated share holders can communicate.

Damage bound. If an attacker compromises one ungated share, they still need a second share. If that second share is gated, the attacker can only sign transactions that pass the full policy suite—capping damage at the policy limit.

Standard MPC signing provides liveness but no damage bounds. Policy enforcement provides damage bounds but no liveness guarantee. The combination provides both from a single key ceremony.

C. Scaling

The approach works well for small groups—up to about 10–15 total co-signing paths—which covers agent wallets and custody services. Beyond that, paths can be grouped by class (e.g., “any path containing a human share”) rather than enumerated individually.

IV. GUARDIAN WALLET

The previous section described signing roles in general terms. We now instantiate the (2, 3) case—the smallest configuration that admits distinct paths—as an MPC wallet for AI agents on Ethereum. Three shares, three roles, three co-signing paths.

A. Three Roles

TABLE II
SHARE ROLES IN GUARDIAN WALLET.

Share	Role	Availability	Storage
s_0	Agent	Always	Encrypted file
s_1	Governor	After policies pass	Vault KV v2
s_2	Sovereign	Always	Passkey (PRF)

The **Agent** holds a share on the agent’s machine—always available, enabling autonomous signing. The **Governor** holds a share on the server, released only when the request passes all policies (spending limits, whitelists, rate limits). The **Sovereign** holds a share bound to a human-owned passkey— independent of any infrastructure. We use the term from the self-sovereign identity literature: the party whose authority is not derived from any infrastructure.

TABLE III
THREE PATHS, THREE AUTHORISATION CONTEXTS.

Path	Context	When
Agent + Governor	Autonomous	Normal operation
Sovereign + Governor	Override	Human intervenes
Agent + Sovereign	Bypass	Emergency / server down

B. Three Signing Paths

Path selection is the authorisation decision. The system does not make an allow/deny choice and then run a generic signing protocol. Instead, which shares participate determines the authority level. The two paths through the Governor enforce policies; the Bypass path excludes the Governor entirely.

C. Architecture

Fig. 1 shows the three trust domains. The Governor’s policy engine gates share access—a rejected request never touches key material. The Bypass path routes around the Governor.

Fig. 1. Guardian Wallet: three trust domains, three co-signing paths. Diamond gates indicate policy checks. The Bypass path (dashed) has no gate—liveness is preserved if the Governor is unavailable.

D. Policy-Gated Signing

Algorithm 2 shows the Governor’s procedure. The share (VAULT.READ, line 7) is loaded only after all policies pass (line 3). Rejected requests never touch key material. The share is wiped in a `finally` block on both success and error paths.

Require: transaction tx , credential k , signing path a

- 1: $s \leftarrow \text{AUTHENTICATE}(k)$
- 2: $V \leftarrow \bigcup_{p \in s.\text{policies}} p(tx, a)$ {all policies, no short-circuit}
- 3: **if** $V \neq \emptyset$ **then**
- 4: $\text{LOG}(\text{REJECTED}, V, a)$; **return** \perp {share never loaded}
- 5: **end if**
- 6: $\text{LOG}(\text{ACCEPTED}, a)$
- 7: $\sigma_1 \leftarrow \text{VAULT.READ}(s.\text{path})$
- 8: **try** $\text{sig} \leftarrow \text{INTERACTIVESIGN}(\sigma_1, tx)$
- 9: **finally** $\sigma_1.\text{fill}(0)$ {zeroed on all paths}
- 10: **return** sig

Fig. 2. Policy-gated signing (Governor). The share is loaded only after all policies pass. Path a is available to policies, enabling path-dependent evaluation.

This coupling is not cryptographic—an attacker who compromises the Governor’s host can modify the code path and

bypass policies. The defence relies on domain separation: bypassing policies on the Governor still yields only one share, not a complete key.

Ten policy types span four categories: *value* (per-tx, daily, monthly limits), *target* (allowed/blocked contracts, function selectors), *rate* (request rate, time windows), and *meta* (custom rules, default-deny).

V. SECURITY

Given the architecture above, we analyse what happens when one trust domain is compromised.

Threat model. An attacker compromises exactly one trust domain, gaining its share and host access. The MPC protocol [1] is assumed secure. Two-domain collusion defeats any 2-of-3 scheme.

Agent compromised. The attacker holds s_0 and needs one more share. The Governor (s_1) only co-signs policy-passing transactions, capping damage at the policy limit. The Bypass path requires the Sovereign’s passkey—a separate physical device.

Governor compromised. The attacker holds s_1 but cannot initiate signing—the Agent or Sovereign must start a session. The attacker would need to intercept a legitimate session.

Sovereign compromised. Co-signing with the Governor remains policy-gated. Co-signing with the Agent requires the Agent to initiate independently.

Worked example. A DeFi agent holds 200ETH with policies: 1ETH per-tx, 5ETH daily, whitelist of three DEX contracts. An attacker compromises the Agent and tries to drain via the Governor path. Sending 200ETH to an attacker address: rejected (limits + whitelist). Sending to a whitelisted DEX within limits: maximum damage 5ETH/day—a 40:1 reduction versus a standard MPC scheme with no policies.

Bypass path risk. The Bypass path has no policy enforcement. Under single-domain corruption it is unreachable (requires both s_0 and s_2 from separate domains). Deploying both shares on the same host would collapse this separation. Security depends on physical domain separation.

Key non-reconstruction. The private key is never reconstructed in any domain. The MPC protocol produces signatures through interactive computation; neither party learns the other’s share or the combined key.

VI. IMPLEMENTATION AND PERFORMANCE

To validate the design, we built Guardian Wallet as a working system and measured its performance. The implementation comprises nine TypeScript packages (~17 000 lines) in a Turborepo monorepo. We use the CGGMP protocol [1] via the `cggmp24` Rust crate (LFDT-Lockness), compiled to WebAssembly for portability and with a native GMP-accelerated binary for production. All measurements on Apple Silicon (M4 Max, 16 GB), localhost, Node.js 22.

Limitation: all benchmarks use localhost. Production deployments would add 30–200 ms depending on network topology (3–4 protocol rounds \times RTT).

A. Key Generation

Key generation is dominated by 2048-bit Paillier prime generation. Pre-computing auxiliary data eliminates this bottleneck.

TABLE IV
KEY GENERATION LATENCY (3 SHARES, THRESHOLD 2).

Backend	Config	Time
WASM	Cold	~200 s
Native (GMP)	Cold	~140 s
Native (GMP)	Cached primes	~15 s
Native (GMP)	Pooled AuxInfo	~1 s

B. Signing

TABLE V
SIGNING LATENCY (AUTONOMOUS PATH, LOCALHOST).

	Native (GMP)	WASM
Median	1 107 ms	~12 700 ms
Mean \pm 95% CI	1 263 \pm 132 ms	—
P5 / P95	940 / 2 125 ms	—
Speedup	11.5 \times	

Native: 30 trials. WASM: 3 trials. WASM is used for browser-side signing (Override path).

C. Policy Overhead and Share Safety

All ten policies evaluated without short-circuit: <2 ms total (<0.02% of signing time). Governor share material loaded from Vault into a `Uint8Array`, zeroed via `buffer.fill(0)` in a `finally` block. Source-level `grep` confirms no key reconstruction paths and no share bytes in logs.

Status. Autonomous and Override paths validated end-to-end on Base Sepolia: message signing, ETH transfer, and contract deployment. Bypass path validated at protocol level (integration tests) but not yet production-exposed.

VII. COMPARISON

Guardian Wallet is not the right choice for every agent wallet scenario. Role-gated MPC wallets target a specific use case: single-team operators who need policy-gated autonomy, human override, and an infrastructure-independent bypass from a single key ceremony. We compare against three alternative approaches.

Smart accounts [15], [16] provide on-chain policy verifiability—every constraint is auditable by third parties. Olas runs 360+ daily agents on Gnosis via Safe, and Brahma Console manages \$300M+ with guard modules. The trade-offs: gas overhead per operation, scope rigidity (permissions fixed at issuance), session keys are complete signing keys within their scope, and the infrastructure is EVM-specific.

Hosted MPC / TEE wallets [8], [17] sign in under 200 ms with no multi-party protocol. Fireblocks serves 2 000+ institutional clients (B2C2, Galaxy Digital); Turnkey powers

Axiom (1M+ users) and Wayfinder (550K wallets). The cost is trust concentration: the entire key sits in one enclave at one provider. A side-channel attack [22] or provider outage exposes or locks everything.

Decentralised MPC [18], [19], [23] distributes shares across independent operators. THORChain uses GG20 TSS [10] for bridge signing; Axelar and Wormhole (13/19 multisig) secure cross-chain transfers. All shares are interchangeable—the protocol cannot express different authority levels for different co-signing groups. Liveness depends on network availability; Lit V1 [19] claims sub-second signing but no independent benchmarks have been published.

Non-collusive 2PC-MPC. [24] takes a different approach to decentralised signing. The protocol splits the key into two shares—a user share and a network share—where the network share is emulated by a large-scale MPC among hundreds of permissionless nodes. The structure is non-collusive: the network alone can never produce a signature, regardless of how many nodes collude. This is a stronger guarantee than standard t -of- n threshold schemes, where any t parties can collude to sign. Ika deploys 2PC-MPC on a Sui-based network with over 100 independent operators and claims sub-second signing latency. Policy enforcement is anchored on-chain via Sui smart contracts, making constraints publicly verifiable—an advantage over operator-trusted policy engines. To realise three operational roles from a two-party protocol, the model requires distributing copies of the same share to multiple holders, which introduces a duplication step where that share must be transferred to multiple parties. This couples the failure domains of holders sharing the same key material. An infrastructure-independent bypass path—one requiring no network availability—is not natively supported without this duplication.

Role-gated MPC wallets (Guardian) combine operator-controlled infrastructure, policy-gated share access, and an infrastructure-independent bypass from a single key ceremony. The target scenarios—DeFi trading agents and AI fund managers that need spending limits with a human bypass—have no verified deployments yet. The costs: 1.1 s latency (excludes MEV), policies are operator-trusted (not publicly verifiable), and self-hosting requires operational capacity.

None of these approaches has signing roles: smart accounts, hosted MPC/TEE wallets, and decentralised MPC all treat co-signers as interchangeable within their respective schemes. These categories are not mutually exclusive—a Safe multisig can include an MPC signer as one owner, and a TEE can serve as one share-holder in an MPC scheme.

VIII. LIMITATIONS

Application-layer enforcement. Roles are enforced by the application, not the cryptographic protocol. Shares are mathematically equivalent after DKG. Cryptographic role binding (e.g., ZK proofs embedding role metadata in the signing protocol) is the primary direction for future work.

Centralised key generation. All three DKG parties run on one host during setup (~ 1 s). A distributed ceremony would eliminate this exposure window.

Unaudited dependency. The CGGMP crate is alpha-stage (v0.7.0). No independent audit has been performed.

Browser latency. Override path via WASM: ~ 12.7 s. Presignatures would reduce this to sub-second.

V8 memory model. The garbage collector may retain copies of wiped buffers. Migrating share handling to WASM linear memory would strengthen erasure.

IX. CONCLUSION

We introduced role-gated MPC wallets: assign distinct roles to MPC shares so that which pair co-signs determines what is allowed. Gating one share fewer than the threshold on policy ensures most co-signing pairs enforce constraints while leaving exactly one emergency bypass—practical for up to about 10–15 co-signing paths. The (2, 3) instantiation as Guardian Wallet validates this with 1.1 s signing latency and under 2 ms policy overhead.

Existing approaches each serve specific use cases well—smart accounts for DAO governance, hosted MPC/TEE wallets for institutional settlement, decentralised MPC for bridge signing—but none combines policy-gated autonomy, human override, and an infrastructure-independent bypass from a single key ceremony. Role-gated MPC wallets address this combination. Whether the construction warrants cryptographic treatment at the protocol layer is a question for future work. The implementation is open source.

AVAILABILITY

Source code: <https://github.com/Agentokratia/guardian-wallet> (AGPL-3.0). CGGMP protocol: LFDLockness `cggmp24` Rust crate (MIT/Apache-2.0), compiled to WebAssembly.

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